

Comparison of Remote Sensing Soil Moisture Algorithms across Optical, Thermal and Radar Classes

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Abstract: As coastal river deltas experience specific climate change and management pressures, monitoring programs are necessary for proper agroecosystem management strategies. This study evaluates the performance and temporal dynamics of multiple remote sensing-derived moisture products and indices against in-situ soil volumetric water content (VWC) measurements collected from January 2021 to December 2022 at Vidrice polder (Neretva River Valley, Croatia). We compared Thermal-Optical Trapezoid Model (TOTRAM), Optical Trapezoid Model (OPTRAM) estimates derived from Landsat-8/9 (L8/L9) and Sentinel-2 (S2), Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) based moisture from Sentinel-1 and spectral indices including Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) and Moisture Stress Index (MSI) from both L8/L9 and S2. All datasets were harmonized to a common temporal scale and merged for direct comparison. Results demonstrate distinct seasonal patterns across most products with S2 OPTRAM showing highest correlation ($r=0.631$) while L8/9 OPTRAM ($r=0.413$) and L8/9 TOTRAM ($r=0.512$) showed moderate correlation with in-situ measurements. SAR-based estimates showed weak correlation likely due to C-band sensitivity to surface roughness and vegetation biomass. Differences in spatial resolution between L8/L9 and S2 were also reflected in simple moisture indices, with ones based on S2 data showing higher alignment ($r=0.466 - 0.505$) with soil moisture measurements. These results suggest that physically-based trapezoid models, particularly when applied to high-resolution optical data like Sentinel-2, provide better representation of soil moisture dynamics than simpler vegetation indices, a desirable factor in soil moisture monitoring.

Keywords: remote sensing; soil moisture index; OPTRAM; TOTRAM; Synthetic Aperture Radar.

1 Introduction

Soil moisture is one of the crucial factors influencing hydrological processes, surface energy balances, agricultural productivity, and climate interactions. Accurately monitoring the temporal and spatial dynamics of soil moisture is essential for optimizing local water management in salinization prone agricultural regions such as the Neretva Valley in Croatia (Lovrinović et al. 2021). Ground-based sensors are inherently limited as point measurements, failing to capture spatial variability

across heterogeneous landscapes (Loconsole et al. 2025). Satellite remote sensing offers a solution for extensive spatial coverage, with optical, thermal, and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) approaches each offering unique advantages and face distinct limitations. Optical and thermal sensors provide high-resolution data that is directly sensitive to chlorophyll content and surface moisture and can be restricted by cloud cover, particularly during the critical autumn and winter months (Casamitjana et al. 2020). Furthermore, C-band SAR sensors, provide all-weather, day-and-night imaging by measuring surface dielectric properties to quantify soil moisture (Bauer-Marschallinger et al. 2019). This study aims to critically evaluate the performance of multiple RS derived soil moisture products against continuous in-situ VWC measurements at a local monitoring site.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Neretva River Valley (NRV) is a coastal floodplain in the south-east of Croatia, a vital agroecosystem for intensive citrus and vegetable production under irrigation. The climate is Mediterranean with dry-hot summers and wet winters. NRV is a low-lying polder system with extensive network of irrigation and drainage infrastructure under heavy influence of the Adriatic Sea via seawater intrusion and river Neretva. Due to these conditions, the groundwater level sits high in the vertical profile, characterizing the soils of area as hydromorphic.

Figure 1. Sensor location within the study area.

2.2 In-situ and remote sensing data

An automatic solar powered measurement station was installed in a mandarin orchard at Vidrice polder (lat. 42.9872064 N, long. 17.5276438 E, Figure 1). The measurement station was equipped with a Frequency Domain Reflectometry – FDR volumetric soil moisture sensor (Meter Group 2022) which collected data from January 2021 to December 2022.

Data was recorded at depth of 25 cm in a 15-minute interval, averaged to hourly and daily values and transmitted wirelessly. Remote sensing data was gathered and processed with Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017) and RStudio version 2025.5.1.513 (Posit team 2025). Data for the entire NRV was queried with cloud coverage of 10% for S2 to 20% for L8/9 within the same duration as in-situ data collection. For SAR data, vertically transmitted and received polarization (VV) was used and a speckle filter was applied while for multispectral (MS) satellites bands from the visible, short-wave infrared and thermal part of the spectra were included (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of RS products.

Satellite mission	Product	Sensor type	Input data	Resolution (m)
Sentinel-1	GRD	SAR	VV	10
Sentinel-2	L2A	MS	B3, B4, B8, B11*, B12*	10, 20*
Landsat 8/9	T1L2	MS	B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B10**	30, 100**

*, ** Specific bands that differ in resolution than majority.

2.3 Data processing

RS data was masked using Dynamic World V1 land use information where water and urban masks were applied on the study area to avoid miscalibration of optical and thermal algorithms. Full expressions for NDMI, MSI and NDWI can be found in the Awesome Spectral Indices GitHub repository (Awesome Spectral Indices 2023).

Calculations of OPTRAM and TOTRAM were done according to a study by Sadeghi et al. (2017). For OPTRAM, the process

begins by calculating NDVI and shortwave infrared transformed reflectance (STR) is derived from the square of the complement of SWIR reflectance as shown in equation (1) in order to create a STR-NDVI pixel distribution space. By analysing this space across the study area and time. A trapezoid was defined by identifying the intercept (i) and slope (s) of wet (w) and dry (d) edges to anchor the model’s physical boundaries. The final soil moisture index is then calculated for each pixel by measuring its relative position between these dry and wet edges as show in equation (2), effectively normalizing the optical signal into a 0–1 moisture scale.

$$STR = \frac{(1-SWIR)^2}{2*SWIR} \tag{1}$$

$$SM_{OPTRAM} = \frac{i_d + s_d * NDVI - STR}{i_d - i_w + (s_d - s_w) * NDVI} \tag{2}$$

As TOTRAM relies on the land surface temperature (LST) data rather than SWIR reflectance, it could be calculated only for L8/9 data (B10). Analog to the OPTRAM model, LST-NDVI pixel distribution space was calculated by defining the wet and dry edges based on cover and temperature extremes and soil moisture can be described for each pixel with equation (3).

$$SM_{TOTRAM} = \frac{i_d + s_d * NDVI - LST}{i_d - i_w + (s_d - s_w) * NDVI} \tag{3}$$

Both models assume a linear relationship for the moisture edges across the vegetation gradient, RS data extracted at the sensor coordinates was harmonized and correlated with in-situ measurements.

3 Results

S1 maintained a consistent revisit schedule with a notable drop in frequency at the end of 2021 due to a malfunction on one of the satellites. In contrast, L8/9 showed significant data gaps, particularly in the autumn and winter months due to cloud cover (Figure 2).

The comparison between VWC and the moisture indices reveals consistent tracking of the seasonal drying and wetting cycles. VWC dynamics is best described with NDMI_{S2} with r=0.505, followed by negative correlation with MSI_{S2} and NDWI_{S2} with r= -0.480 and -0.466 respectively. NDMI and MSI indices were closer to ground truth measurements in the wetter periods of the year than during the summer. S2 derived indices, provided tighter alignment with the ground sensor measurements than the Landsat equivalents (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Monthly satellite data acquisition frequency for Sentinel-2, Sentinel-1 descending and ascending orbits, and Landsat 8/9 at NRV, January 2021 – December 2022.

Figure 3. Temporal comparison of in-situ volumetric water content (VWC) and satellite-derived soil moisture estimates from A) Landsat 8/9 and Sentinel-1 moisture indices (MSI, NDMI, NDWI), B) S1 SAR (sm_asc, sm_des), and C) optical trapezoid models (OPTRAM, TOTRAM) for the Vidrice site, 2021–2022.

While the ascending (sm_asc) and descending (sm_des) SAR data displayed significant high-frequency variance, the application of a LOESS smoother effectively clarified the underlying soil moisture signal in both passes. The sm_asc orbit demonstrated a somewhat better overall tracking of the seasonal cycles than the sm_des orbit, with $r=0.258$ and 0.200 respectively. Narrower convergence of VWC and sm_asc was observed during the 2021 season (Figure 2).

Both the OPTRAM and TOTRAM models demonstrated statistically significant capabilities in tracking in-situ VWC, though with varying levels of accuracy. The OPTRAM_{S2} was the top performer among the soil moisture products, yielding the highest correlation ($r=0.631$) and the lowest Root Mean Square Error (RMSE=0.113) with high significance ($p<0.01$). Although OPTRAM_{L8L9} maintained a statistically significant relationship ($p<0.01$), it resulted in a lower correlation ($r=0.413$). Despite having a statistically significant relationship with in-situ measurements ($p<0.01$) TOTRAM_{L8L9} showed moderate correlation ($r=0.512$). Despite some differences, these models captured dry conditions observed in the summer of 2021, though the Sentinel-2 implementation provided a more precise alignment across the wider dynamic range of soil moisture (Figure 3).

4 Discussion

Correlations observed between VWC and the S2 derived moisture indices validate the use of optimized spectral bands for monitoring soil moisture. These results align with previous studies that have identified the sensitivity of SWIR bands to vegetation and surface water content (Lobell and Asner 2002). The stronger performance of S2 indices compared to their L8/9 can likely be attributed to S2's higher spatial resolution and its more frequent revisit time, which allowed for a more precise capture of soil moisture dynamics despite cloud cover. MSI and NDWI correlation direction is consistent and can be explained with their respective formulations. For MSI, increasing soil moisture triggers a drop in SWIR reflectance due to water absorption, thereby reducing the index value (Welikhe et al. 2017). Similarly, in NDWI the high NIR reflectance associated with healthy, hydrated surfaces is subtracted from the green band, causing the index to become more negative as moisture content increases (Koohikeradeh et al. 2025). In context of S1 data, differences between the ascending and descending passes could stem from variation in night/day acquisition time. Even with high frequency acquisition and with speckle filtering applied, the data was still noisy, likely due to vegetation canopy volume scattering (De Petris et al., 2021). This in effect lowers the usability of C-band SAR data soil moisture monitoring in orchards. The performance of OPTRAM_{S2}

validates the efficacy of utilizing the STR-NDVI feature space for this case. This result aligns with the fundamental premise of the OPTRAM approach, as detailed by Sadeghi et al. (2017) that STR effectively captures the response of soil moisture across a gradient of vegetation density.

5 Conclusions

Between all compared approaches in this study area, OPTRAM_{s2} is the most effective satellite-derived soil moisture monitoring in irrigated orchards experiencing soil salinity stress, outperforming L8/9 trapezoidal models, SAR C-band products and conventional moisture indices. Success can be attributed to high spatio-temporal resolution as well as robust feature space parameterization through time. However, moderate overall correlation values point to inherent limitations, as can occur when simplifying complex land surface interactions that are impacted by factors such as mixed pixels due to spatial resolution, surface heterogeneity, or diverse vegetation responses that are not solely dependent on soil moisture.

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